

ISSUES OF DEVELOPING INCLUSIVE COMPETENCE IN FUTURE TEACHERS BASED ON A COGNITIVE APPROACH.

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ABSTRACT

The article focuses on improving the content and teaching methods of higher pedagogical education based on theoretical approaches to cognitive pedagogy, and the specific features of developing inclusive competence in future teachers based on a cognitive approach.

Keywords: future teacher, inclusive competence, higher pedagogical education, cognitive education, knowledge, cognitive approach, pedagogical activity.

ANNOTATSIYA

Maqolada kognitiv pedagogikaga oid nazariy yondashuvlar asosida oliy pedagogik ta'lim mazmuni va o'qitish metodlarini takomillashtirish, kognitiv yondashuv asosida bo'lajak o'qituvchilarda inklyuziv kompetensiyasini rivojlantirishning o'ziga xos xususiyatlariga e'tibor qaratilgan.

Tayanch so'zlar: bo'lajak o'qituvchi, inklyuziv kompetensiyasi, oliy pedagogik ta'lim, kognitiv ta'lim, bilim, kognitiv yondashuv, pedagogik faoliyat.

АННОТАЦИЯ

В статье рассматриваются вопросы совершенствования содержания и методов обучения высшего педагогического образования на основе теоретических подходов к когнитивной педагогике, а также особенности формирования инклюзивной компетентности будущих учителей на основе когнитивного подхода.

Ключевые слова: будущий учитель, инклюзивная компетентность, высшее педагогическое образование, когнитивное образование, знания, когнитивный подход, педагогическая деятельность.

The preservation and development of knowledge in human memory and thinking is the basis for the emergence of cognitive activity and inclusive competence. Cognitive activity formed in future teachers is the main source of inclusive competence. Today, cognitive pedagogy is approached worldwide as a field of science that embodies all the knowledge inherent in human activity. This, in turn, creates the need to effectively use the capabilities of cognitive pedagogy in training future teachers and forming inclusive competence in them. The development of inclusive competence in future teachers based on a cognitive approach is in line with the goals of educational reforms being implemented in our Republic and is an important step in the development of cognitive pedagogy. One of the leading methods of cognitive pedagogy is the method of retrospective analysis.

This method allows for a comprehensive study and in-depth analysis of many areas and ideas in the field of training future teachers based on a cognitive approach. These ideas, teachings, and concepts serve to identify promising areas for developing inclusive competence in future teachers. The development of inclusive competence in future teachers is directly related to the cognitive process of a person. The cognitive process of a person represents the systematic manifestation of mental processes. These are expressed in the perception, retention, recall, processing, and interpretation of professional knowledge by a future teacher.

The effective methods and techniques that activate these processes in education began to be systematically studied by specialists at the end of the last century. In cognitive pedagogy, activating the future teacher, forming an active attitude towards the educational process has become one of the leading issues. In this regard, special attention is paid to the development of inclusive competence by accelerating the cognitive activity of the future teacher.

Today, special attention is paid to the scientific substantiation of the following areas in cognitive pedagogy. They are:

- development of technologies for the development of cognitive processes of future teachers;
- development of inclusive competence in future teachers by identifying opportunities for activating their personal cognitive processes;
- theoretical substantiation of the fact that the professional perspectives of future teachers are a factor in the independent development of their cognitive spheres and themselves.

In the development of inclusive competence of future teachers based on the cognitive approach, it is envisaged to give priority to the following methods:

1. Reproductive;
2. Heuristics that encourage inquiry;
3. Creative methods.

It is clear that cognitive pedagogy has made it possible to discover a new area of research. Cognitive pedagogy increases the need to use cognitive technologies that serve to expand the creative potential of the individual.

Today, scientific approaches to improving the content and teaching methods of higher pedagogical education are emerging, based on theoretical approaches to cognitive pedagogy. There is a growing need to improve teaching forms and methods that allow the development of inclusive competence of future teachers, and to harmonize philosophical, sociological, psychological, and pedagogical knowledge related to the professional and methodological formation of a person.

The results of the analysis of the content of higher pedagogical education show that the topics, educational materials, cognitive technologies, and training modules that allow for the professional development of future teachers based on a cognitive approach are not sufficiently included in the content [2].

In order to develop inclusive competence in future teachers, it is necessary to ensure that the educational process is manifested as a cognitive system of intellectual, spiritual, cultural, moral, and professional development of the future specialist. When improving the content of higher pedagogical education based on a cognitive approach, special attention should be paid to the development of professional thinking of the process subjects. When developing the inclusive competence of the subjects of the higher pedagogical education process based on a cognitive approach, it is necessary to pay attention to the following - creating a favorable didactic environment for future teachers to manifest themselves as subjects of the creative pedagogical process; - achieving success in their creative development process; - create favorable conditions for the manifestation of their intellectual and creative potential;

- create motivation for their professional development;
- create a favorable pedagogical environment for their creative activity;
- apply strategies for the development of inclusive competence in future teachers;
- pay special attention to enriching the professional culture of future teachers.

To successfully address these challenges, future teachers need to systematically develop inclusive competence. The training of future teachers should in the current era of great challenges, it is of particular importance to ensure an effective solution to

this problem. This requires future teachers to have the competence to independently master cognitive knowledge and effectively apply it in various non-standard pedagogical situations. As a result of developing inclusive competence in future teachers, the knowledge acquired by them is activated, the culture of inclusive competence in future teachers, and the motivation to carry out creative pedagogical activities are strengthened. In order to develop inclusive competence in future teachers, it is advisable to incorporate creative technologies into the content of training modules.

Also, creative cooperation between future teachers and professors, joint analysis of educational materials, and active dialogue are important. Because the inclusive competence of future teachers is manifested in the process of dialogue. The application of a cognitive approach to the process of higher pedagogical education helps future teachers to master creative thinking methods. The theoretical foundations of the cognitive approach are scientific approaches to the process of cognition of a person and its structural structure. Professor R.G. Safarova, reflecting on theoretical approaches to cognitive pedagogy, noted the following: "Cognitive pedagogy puts forward scientific approaches to how and by what means students study the world, organize their activities and implement their lifestyle. Based on the above analysis, it can be noted that the process of developing inclusive competence in future teachers based on a cognitive approach requires the implementation of the following:

- successful solution of tasks related to the development of inclusive competence of future teachers in the process of higher pedagogical education;
- support and development of motivations for inclusive competence of future teachers;
- activation of motivations for knowledge of future teachers based on a cognitive approach;
- transformation of the desire to acquire inclusive competence into an internal need of future teachers;
- these areas must be taken into account when creating curricula, lecture texts, manuals and recommendations for the higher pedagogical education system.

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